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Research integrity at stake: conflicts of interest and industry ties in scientific publications

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Introduction

Conflicts of interest (CoI), also known as competing interest, in scientific research are frequent and may arise in a variety of daily activities: when reviewing scientific articles or grant proposals, developing and reporting research findings or serving on advisory boards.

Thompson (1993, p. 573) refers to CoI as “a set of conditions in which professional judgment concerning a primary interest (such as a patient's welfare or the validity of research) is unduly influenced by a secondary interest (such as financial gain).” Although the definition of CoI is contentious, and the concept is used in different and somehow inconsistent ways (Brody, 2011), there is a broad consensus that they can compromise the integrity of scientific research. If not managed properly, these CoI may, in some instances, represent a severe form of researchers' misconduct and even undermine public trust in science. For this reason, international bodies such as UNESCO have called for mechanisms to protect scientific research from vested interests (Ruff, 2015). To minimise such threats, research organisations¹ and funding agencies² have developed policies to support researchers in managing potential CoI. In addition, scientific journals often require authors to disclose funding sources and any possible CoI at stake. For instance, the Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) has made available a ‘disclosure form’ to help authors reveal CoI in a standardised way, and all ICMJE member journals request it. Similar examples apply to many other journals.

¹ See for instance the cases of University College London (<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/enterprise/about/governanceand-policies/ucl-disclosure-conflict-and-declaration-interest-policy>), the University of South Australia (<https://www.unisa.edu.au/research/integrity/responsible-research-practice/managing-conflicts-of-interest/>). ² For example: <https://wellcome.org/grant-funding/guidance/intellectual-property-guidance/conflicts-interestpolicy-wellcome-funded-researchers-and-commercial-organisations>

CoI are often classified as financial (tangible) or non-financial (intangible), depending on their nature. Receiving research funds from private companies, performing consultancy work for the private sector or holding stocks in a company are just a few examples of potential financial CoI. Personal or professional bonds are subject to non-financial CoI. For instance, an author that is a relative of the editor of a particular journal where he/she submits an article or a researcher who conducts a review perceives a competing interest with his/her own research (e.g. ideological, contrasting findings). These scenarios reflect something of utmost importance; individual researchers are ultimately responsible for disclosing a CoI. Failing to do so represents a form of academic misconduct, which may eventually undermine the credibility and trust in individual researchers, scientific journals and the overall scientific enterprise.

CoI can occur in many different settings. Those related to public research are particularly important given the critical role of public-industry partnership for innovation and the proven commercial interest of industry in gearing research and biasing results towards their own interest (e.g. Fabbri et al., 2018). Much of the research around CoI has focused on biomedical areas, especially in clinical research, where studies are often sponsored by large private corporations (Sismondo, 2008). Previous research has mostly investigated CoI through two pathways: looking into the requirements stated by journals in their authors' guidelines (see, for instance, Rowan-Legg et al., 2009) or examining public-industry partnerships in scientific publications (Lewison & Sullivan, 2015). Particularly interesting is the latter since it allows deepening researchers' individual behaviour and shed light on the variety of potential CoI that arise in practice.

Large-scale and systematic analysis of CoI remained largely untapped due to major scientific databases' lack of indexing (Giles & Council, 2004). The situation changed in 2008 when the Web of Science (WoS) started to collect information on the funding acknowledgements of scientific publications. This has led to a renewed interest in analysing acknowledgements as paratextual traces of research practices (Desrochers et al., 2016). Nevertheless, most studies on the topic have been confined to the analysis of trends and patterns related to funding sources (for a review, see Álvarez-Bornstein and Montesi, 2021) or have dealt with acknowledgements as sources that provide new insights on influential contributions to scientific work (Cronin, Shaw & La Barre, 2003; Giles & Council, 2004; Díaz-Faes & Bordons, 2014). However, few studies have provided fine-grained analyses of CoI statements. A worth mentioning exception is Lewison & Sullivan (2015), who studied the presence of CoI financial statements on a sample of nearly 200,000 papers but focused only on the top 10 pharmaceutical companies in terms of R&D expenditures at that time. In this study, however, we conduct a large-scale analysis of CoI statements related to public-private partnerships, based on scientific outputs published between 2010 and 2020, to address the questions as follows:

- 1) *What percentage of publications include CoI linked to the industry?*
- 2) *What is the distribution of publications disclosing CoI across research domains?*
- 3) *What industry ties are more frequently mentioned as representing potential CoI?*

Data and method

The dataset used in our study was extracted from the CWTS in-house version of the WoS (Arts and Humanities Citation Index, Social Citation Index and Social Sciences Citation Index and Conference Proceedings Citation Index). It includes the full text of the acknowledgements sections of papers for all articles and reviews published between 2010 and 2020, providing that one business company is mentioned in the funding acknowledgement of the publication,

as recorded by WoS. Only for-profit business companies were considered since it is in such companies where CoI are more likely to emerge. Therefore, other entities such as companies that provide healthcare services, foundations related to private firms (e.g. Novo Nordisk Foundation) or educational entities, such as private universities, were excluded from the analysis.

Processing of funding acknowledgements

Clarivate's WoS started to include information on funding acknowledgements disclosed in scientific publications in August 2008. WoS collects all acknowledgement types for all such entries, including CoI statements (Díaz-Faes & Bordons, 2015; Lewison & Sullivan, 2015).

We isolated CoI from other types of information included in the funding acknowledgement text, such as statements acknowledging funding provided to perform the published research. We did this by parsing the full text of the acknowledgement included in WoS in a two-step procedure. First, we identified the specific sentences in which private companies were mentioned, discarding all the other sentences in which for-profit companies were not named (e.g., they might refer to public funders). Second, we established a number of rules of thumb to detect CoI statements. Typically, a CoI includes a reference to one or several authors of the publication and lists specific activities and roles associated with CoI, such as being an employee, consultant, member of an advisory board, an investigator in a clinical trial, shareholder, and speaker, among others. As a result of a detailed inspection of many of the funding acknowledgements, we collected a long list of keywords and expressions used in CoI. In this way, we were able to identify publications with statements such as: “*Author X has served as a speaker for company Y*” or “*Author Z has received research funding from Y*”.

Scientific landscape

To visualise COI statements' distributions by research domains, we relied on the publication classification system developed at CWTS (Waltman & van Eck, 2012). The classification has a three-level structure, in which the macro-level has 21 broad disciplines, the meso-level 838 fields and the micro-level 4,159 subfields. A computer algorithm assigns each publication to one of these clusters by analysing hundreds of millions of citation relations between publications.

Preliminary results and discussion

The global map of research domains evidence that no more than a small minority of scientific publications include industry ties related to CoI ($\approx 1.5\%$ of all publications in the period 2010-2020). Figure 1 shows a map of research domains clustered by citation links between publications. CoI are mainly concentrated in biomedical and health sciences.

Yellow nodes in the map represent clusters of publications with a relatively high proportion of articles including CoI, while blue nodes indicate a low presence of CoI statements. Only a few exceptions are found in clusters related to life and earth sciences (centre of the map).

This first finding is consistent with observations from previous studies such as Paul-Hus et al. (2017).

Figure 1. Map of publications disclosing CoI in the scientific landscape.

Table 1 summarises the proportion of publications with CoI statements by field and subfields for the top 10 clusters of publications, ranging from 14% to 19%. Some clusters are related to diabetes, obesity, endocrinology, and metabolism (106, 1004), while others relate to cardiology (422, 761), blood-related problems such as thrombosis or haemophilia (1172, 474, 761), dermatology (472) or psychiatry (263). These clusters of publications belong to research domains of activity for both pharmaceutical and medical devices companies.

Table 1. Cluster with the highest percentages of publications disclosing CoIs

Cluster	Labels	Journals	% with CoI
106	sodium glucose cotransporter; empagliflozin; sgl2 inhibitor; insulin degludec; sgl2	Diabetes Care; Diabetes Obesity & Metabolism; Diabetes Technology & Therapeutics; Diabetic Medicine; Diabetes Research And Clinical Practice	19.0%
1172	haemophilium; recombinant factor viia; inhibitor development; haemophilia patient	Haemophilia; Journal Of Thrombosis And Haemostasis; Thrombosis And Haemostasis; Blood Coagulation & Fibrinolysis; Blood	18.3%
3079	pure red cell aplasia; biosimilar; large granular lymphocyte leukemia; infliximab biosimilar; oncology	Biodrugs; Annals Of The Rheumatic Diseases; Biologicals; Expert Opinion On Biological Therapy; British Journal Of Haematology	17.5%
474	direct oral anticoagulant; venous thromboembolism; warfarin; rivaroxaban; stroke prevention	Thrombosis Research; Journal Of Thrombosis And Thrombolysis; Thrombosis And Haemostasis; International Journal Of Cardiology; Journal Of Thrombosis And Haemostasis	16.5%
472	psoriasis; severe plaque psoriasis; ustekinumab; apremilast; phototherapy	British Journal Of Dermatology; Journal Of The European Academy Of Dermatology And Venereology; Journal Of The American Academy Of Dermatology; Journal Of Dermatological Treatment; Journal Of Rheumatology	15.8%

1004	exendin; dipeptidyl peptidase iv; receptor; gip; peptide	Diabetes Obesity & Metabolism; Diabetes; Diabetes Care; Plos One; Journal Of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism	15.6%
422	cardiac resynchronization therapy; biventricular pacing; implantable cardioverter	Pace-Pacing And Clinical Electrophysiology; Europace; Heart Rhythm; Journal Of Cardiovascular Electrophysiology; International	15.6%
	defibrillator; transvenous lead extraction; ventricular dyssynchrony	Journal Of Cardiology	
263	tardive dyskinesia; weight gain; antipsychotic induced weight gain; paliperidone palmitate; hyperprolactinemia	Journal Of Clinical Psychopharmacology; Journal Of Clinical Psychiatry; Schizophrenia Research; Psychiatric Services; American Journal Of Psychiatry	15.0%
761	ticagrelor; clopidogrel; aspirin resistance; prasugrel; cilostazol	Thrombosis And Haemostasis; Platelets; Journal Of The American College Of Cardiology; Thrombosis Research; American Journal Of Cardiology	14.9%
139	early rheumatoid arthritis; peptide antibody; synovioocyte; collagen; anti cyclic	Annals Of The Rheumatic Diseases; Journal Of Rheumatology; Rheumatology; Arthritis & Rheumatism-Arthritis Care & Research; Clinical And Experimental Rheumatology	14.1%

When textual patterns are examined in detail, a wide range of activities appears to be related to potential CoI, as shown in Figure 2. Each node in the map represents a term or noun phrase used by authors in scientific publications to refer to a specific tie with industry, while the node's size accounts for the co-occurrence of such a term. If two terms or noun phrases are named in the same publication, this indicates a link between their particular topics, and they will tend to appear close on the map. The map evidence that authors and companies hold a variety of ties. The activities most frequently mentioned refer to consultancy work performed for companies and acting as an advisor. Dark blue nodes point to authors that are also employees of the mentioned companies. Red nodes, however, account for a cluster of terms related to editorial assistance received by the authors. Other activities such as acting as a speaker, holding stocks, receiving royalties, and research grants are also represented on the map.

Science Inc.’ to analyse the role of firms in the landscape of scientific research. The evidence presented also pointed to an overall decline in scientific research performed by companies, with some exceptions such as research in life sciences (especially relevant for sectors like pharma and biotech), where the signs of decline were not found (Arora et al., 2019). However, this seemingly decline in the performance on internal R&D does not mean that scientific research is less important now for the private sector than in the past. All these developments seem to be more related to strategies deployed by firms in order increasingly rely on R&D partners from the public sector and, in doing so, to minimise risks in R&D investments and benefit from new ideas, knowledge and existing talent in the public sector. Thus, these trends suggest that CoI might be even more present in the future.

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